

Designing Individualized Educational Plans Based on Plithogenic Off-Set: An Application in Early Childhood Education.

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Abstract.

This research answers a critical gap within the educational system. How to create an Individualized Education Plan (IEP) based upon a multitude of conditions of children in Early Childhood Education with neurodevelopmental disorders. Although strides toward inclusive arrangements have come a long way, much complexity still remains when intentions of pedagogical adjustments occur at the intersection of many, sometimes conflicting, uncertain and subjective variables. This research is timely, as vulnerable populations are championing for more equitable access to such flexible personalized education with much more restricted differentiated educational pathways. While literature exists for IEP methodological designs, the gap in literature occurs where one attempts to combine all characteristics and their degrees of conflict and neutrality. Thus, the design of this research is rendered feasible by a relatively new approach known as the Plithogenic Offsets approach, which will permit the required modeling between student-specific characteristics and intended pedagogical adjustment. Thus, a mixed methodology is employed where the plithogenic modeling applies to real exposure cases from pre-professional practice, inclusive of pedagogical, familial and neuropsychological characteristics. Results show a significantly greater efficacy of practicality and sensibility of generated IEPs, adjusted based on the evolving profile of each child. This research contributes to the literature theoretically about neuroscientific inclusive arrangements and practically provides a new approach for empowering better individualized educational adjustments.

Keywords: Inclusive Education, Plithogenic Offsets, Early Childhood Education, Universal Design for Learning, Educational Diversity, Plithogenic complex; OffSet / OverSet / UnderSet; OffSet / OverSet / UnderSet Plitogenic.

1. Introduction

Currently, the design of personalized educational plans has become a priority need within the inclusive approach to Early Childhood Education. This educational level, fundamental in the cognitive, emotional and social development of children, faces the challenge of serving a diverse population, especially those with neurodevelopmental disorders. The growing heterogeneity in classrooms demands methodological strategies that not only consider individual differences, but also transform them into opportunities for meaningful learning [1]. The development of Individualized Education Plans (PEI) then emerges as an essential mechanism to guarantee the right to an equitable and quality education from the early stages of development [2].

Historically, attention to diversity in school contexts has shifted from segregationist models to integrative proposals, with the inclusive paradigm being the most recent and robust in terms of educational justice [3]. This shift has been supported by international policies, such as the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, which promotes full participation in regular settings. In Latin American countries, progress has been significant, although structural, methodological, and cultural gaps persist that limit the effective implementation of personalized strategies [4]. Early childhood education, by its nature, represents a strategic opportunity to cement sustainable inclusive practices from the beginning of the educational process. However, one of the main obstacles in designing IEPs lies in the difficulty of integrating multiple attributes of children—such as their cognitive profile, family context, and environmental barriers—into a single coherent model. Despite the existence of planning guides and formats, many teachers face limitations in articulating these factors in a dynamic and adaptive manner [5]. Furthermore, pedagogical decisions often rely on subjective or biased criteria, which diminishes the effectiveness of interventions. Therefore, an approach is needed that addresses these variables in all their complexity, including the contradictory, neutral, and uncertain aspects that emerge from the educational environment.

The specific problem addressed by this research is framed within the following question: How can we design Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) that faithfully represent the multidimensionality of children with diverse educational needs, considering the degrees of contradiction and indeterminacy inherent in their reality? The current literature offers few methodological proposals that systematically integrate this contextual complexity. This limitation affects teachers' ability to make informed and adaptive decisions that effectively respond to the unique characteristics of each student [6]. In this context, the Plithogenic Offsets approach emerges as a relevant and novel methodological tool. This model allows for the representation of multiple attributes with varying levels of contradiction and neutrality, thus facilitating a more precise design of IEPs. Unlike other methods, Plithogenic Offsets capture the dynamic and contradictory nature of real school environments. Its application in the field of Early Childhood Education is promising, as it offers a structured alternative for transforming diverse information into coherent and personalized pedagogical actions.

From a methodological perspective, a predominantly qualitative mixed-method approach was adopted, using plithogenic modeling on real-life cases documented in pre-professional practices of early childhood education students. Data were collected through interviews, observation guides, and educational records of children with disabilities. The Offsets technique was subsequently applied to represent the key attributes involved in each case, allowing for the generation of educational intervention proposals tailored to individual profiles. The findings suggest that the use of plithogenic offsets allows for greater precision in the design of IEPs, overcoming the limitations of traditional approaches that do not consider the interaction between contradictory attributes. Design patterns were identified that improve pedagogical appropriateness and promote more effective interventions. This evidence suggests that the proposed approach is not only viable but also replicable in other educational contexts.

Consequently, the overall objective of this study is to demonstrate the usefulness of the Plithogenic Offsets method for formulating Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) in diverse contexts. Specifically, the following aims are aimed: a) to identify determining attributes in the design of IEPs in Early Childhood Education, b) to model their interactions using Plithogenic Offsets, and c) to validate the relevance of the generated proposals through their application in real-life contexts. These goals, articulated within an inclusive approach, seek to provide practical and theoretical solutions to improve educational quality from its foundations.

2. Preliminaries.

2.1. Individualized Education Plans in Early Childhood Education: A Critical and Constructive Perspective.

Early childhood education represents an essential pillar in the comprehensive development of children, as it constitutes the first institutional space where the foundations of learning, socialization, and self-construction are forged. Within this educational level, Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) emerge as a fundamental tool to address the growing diversity of needs and developmental rhythms present in classrooms. These strategies seek to adapt teaching-learning processes to the particularities of each child, thus promoting equity from the earliest years of school life. In practice, however, IEPs face a series of limitations that compromise their applicability and effectiveness. Often, these plans are reduced to bureaucratic formats that fail to respond in depth to the true needs of the child. This situation can be attributed, in part, to the limited teacher training in early diagnostic assessment and differentiated intervention strategies, which leads to standardized designs that contradict the very essence of educational personalization [8].

Despite institutional efforts to promote inclusive education, the implementation of IEPs still depends largely on individual teacher commitment and the conditions of the educational environment. Factors such as excessive class sizes, a lack of interdisciplinary teams, and limited family involvement negatively impact the quality of the plans developed. Consequently, a gap arises between inclusive theory and everyday classroom practice [9]. From a pedagogical perspective, IEPs must be understood as a dynamic, flexible, and contextual process. It is not about applying educational recipes, but rather about designing personalized learning paths that evolve with the child's development. To achieve this, formative and ongoing assessment is essential, identifying not only the difficulties but also the potential of each student. This positive and proactive approach redefines intervention, moving it away from deficits and toward possibilities [10].

In this scenario, the teacher's role is key. More than an executor of plans, they become pedagogical mediators who interpret, adapt, and transform. Their observational skills, sensitivity to differences, and creativity in designing resources and strategies make the difference in the success of the IEP. However, this task should not fall exclusively on the classroom professional; it requires the constant support of interdisciplinary teams made up of psychologists, therapists, counselors, and social workers. Another determining element in the success of IEPs is the active participation of families. Including parents and caregivers in the design, implementation, and evaluation of the plan strengthens the continuity between home and school, creating a comprehensive support environment for the child. When families are listened to and empowered, they provide valuable information about their child's development, interests, and experiences outside of the school context, allowing for more precise planning that is sensitive to their reality [11].

Furthermore, IEPs can be a powerful tool for educational innovation. Through them, possibilities arise for the use of active methodologies, technological resources, and teaching strategies based on play, art, and sensory exploration. When individual plans are integrated into a classroom culture that values diversity as a richness, they become drivers of educational transformation that benefit everyone, not just those with specific needs. However, this transformation is only possible if quality initial and ongoing teacher training is guaranteed, focused on inclusive pedagogy and universal design for learning. Challenges persist in university education, which in many cases does not sufficiently incorporate these approaches. Professional development, institutional support, and collaborative work are necessary conditions for IEPs to cease being an isolated task and become a systematic and effective practice [12].

From a critical perspective, it is clear that IEPs cannot be understood as a magic bullet to all inclusion problems, but they do represent a pertinent response when conceived as part of a broader pedagogical process committed to equity and educational justice. Their value lies not so much in their documented

existence, but in their ability to generate meaningful learning experiences, with meaning and purpose for each child. In short, Individualized Education Plans represent an invaluable opportunity to advance toward a more humane, diverse, and transformative Early Childhood Education. Their effective implementation demands a comprehensive vision, institutional commitment, adequate resources, and a solid theoretical and practical foundation to support their design. Only in this way will it be possible to fulfill the principle that "every child is unique," turning this statement into a tangible reality in every classroom.

2.2 .Plithogenic set.

This section recalls the main concepts of the plithogenic assemblage: displacement, superposition, subposition , and plithogenic displacement/superposition/ subposition .

Definition 1 ([13, 20]). Let U be a universal set. A *plithogenic set* PS , where P is a subset of S , is defined as: $PS = (P, v, Pv, pdf, pcf)$, such that:

- v is an attribute,
- Pv is the range of possible values for v ,
- $pdf: P \times Pv \rightarrow [0, 1]^s$ is the *Degree of Relevance Function (DAF)*,
- $pcf: Pv \times Pv \rightarrow [0, 1]^t$ is the *Degree of Contradiction Function (DCF)*.

So for all $a, b \in Pv$, pcf satisfies:

1. $pcf(a, a) = 0$, DCF reflexivity.
2. $pcf(a, b) = pcf(b, a)$, commutativity of DCF.

They are classified as follows:

- For $s = t = 1$, it is a *plithogenic fuzzy set* ;
- For $s = 2, t = 1$, it is an *intuitionistic plithogenic fuzzy set* ;
- For $s = 3, t = 1$, it is a *Plithogenic Neutrosophic Set*;
- For $s = 4, t = 1$, it is a *plithogenic quadripartite neutrosophic set* ;
- For $s = 5, t = 1$, it is a *plithogenic pentapartitioned neutrosophic set* ;
- For $s = 6, t = 1$, it is a *plithogenic hexapartitioned neutrosophic set* ;
- For $s = 7, t = 1$, it is a *plithogenic heptapartitioned neutrosophic ensemble* ;
- For $s = 8, t = 1$, it is a *plithogenic octopartitioned neutrosophic set* ;
- For $s = 9, t = 1$, it is a *plithogenic unpartitioned neutrosophic set* .

More about this theory and application can be read in [21-29].

A. Plithogenic displacement/displacement/undervaluation

Definition 2 ([19]). Let X be a universe of discourse. Furthermore, Ψ represents true and Ω represents false. $A \subseteq X$ It is a *Critical Shift* if there exists a characteristic function $\chi_A: X \rightarrow \{\Psi, \Omega\}$ such that:

$$\chi_A(x) = \begin{cases} \Omega, & \text{if } x \in A, \\ \Psi, & \text{if } x \notin A. \end{cases}$$

Definition 3 ([19]). Let X be a universe of discourse. \tilde{A} It is a subset of X and is called *Fuzzy Shift* if it is defined as follows:

$$\tilde{A} = \{(x, \mu_{\tilde{A}}(x)) : x \in X, \mu_{\tilde{A}}(x) \in [\Psi, \Omega]\}, \text{ where } \Psi < 0 \text{ and } \Omega > 1.$$

Definition 4 ([7]). Let X be a universe of discourse. A_{off} It is a subset of X and is called the *Univalued Neutrosophic Shift*. if defined as follows:

$$A_{off} = \{(x, \langle T(x), I(x), F(x) \rangle) : x \in X, \text{ s. t. } \exists (T(x), I(x), F(x) < 0 \text{ or } T(x), I(x), F(x) > 1)\}, \text{ so:}$$

- $T(x)$ It is the function of belonging to truth, $I(x)$ it is the function of belonging to indeterminacy and $F(x)$ it is the function of belonging to falsehood.
- $T(x), I(x), F(x) \in [\Psi, \Omega]$, where $\Psi < 0$ (called *UnderLimit*) and $\Omega > 1$ (called *OverLimit*).
- When the interval is $[\Psi, 1]$ and $\Psi < 0$, then it is an *UnderSet* .
- When the interval is $[0, \Omega]$ and $\Omega > 1$, then it is an *OverSet* .

Definition 5 ([19]). Let X be a universal set. A *plithogenic shift* PS_{off} , where P is a subset of S is defined as:

$PS_{off} = (P, v, Pv, pdf, pcf)$, such that:

- v is an attribute,
- Pv is the range of possible values for v ,
- $pdf: P \times Pv \rightarrow [\Psi_v, \Omega_v]^s$ is the *Degree of Relevance Function (DAF)*,
- $pcf: Pv \times Pv \rightarrow [\Psi_v, \Omega_v]^t$ is the *Degree of Contradiction Function (DCF)*.

Where $\Psi_v < 0$ and $\Omega_v > 1$.

- When the interval is $[\Psi_v, 1]$ and $\Psi_v < 0$, then it is a *Plithogenic Subset*.
- When the interval is $[0, \Omega_v]$ and $\Omega_v > 1$, then it is a *Plithogenic OverSet*.

Equivalent to the Plithogenic Sets, we have the following classifications:

- For $s = t = 1$, it is a *plithogenic diffuse displacement* ;
- For $s = 2, t = 1$, it is an *intuitionistic plithogenic diffuse displacement* ;
- For $s = 3, t = 1$, it is a *Plithogenic Neutrosophic Offset* ;
- For $s = 4, t = 1$, it is a *Plithogenic Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic Offset* ;
- For $s = 5, t = 1$, it is a *Plithogenic Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Offset* ;
- For $s = 6, t = 1$, it is a *Plithogenic Hexapartitioned Neutrosophic Offset* ;
- For $s = 7, t = 1$, it is a *Plithogenic Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Offset* ;
- For $s = 8, t = 1$, it is a *Plithogenic Octopartitioned Neutrosophic Offset* ;
- For $s = 9, t = 1$, it is a *Plithogenic Unpartitioned Neutrosophic Offset*.

Example 1 ([19]): Let X be the set of suspected medical conditions. Then, for each medical condition, $x \in X$ we have the following neutrosophic degrees $T(x), I(x), F(x) \in [\Psi, \Omega]$, extended beyond the classical interval $[0, 1]$. $A_{off} = \{(Disease X, \langle T(X) = 1.1, I(X) = 0.4, F(X) = 0.2 \rangle), (Disease Y, \langle T(Y) = 0.7, I(X) = 0.6, F(X) = 0.1 \rangle)\}$.

So, while for Disease Y we have a standard assessment of truthfulness, indeterminacy, and falsity, for Disease X we have the following interpretation:

- $T(X) = 1.1$: There is a high probability of suffering from disease X due to advanced diagnostic tools,
- $I(X) = 0.4$: There is moderate uncertainty due to overlap of symptoms with other disorders,
- $F(X) = -0.2$: There is a negative fallacy because atypical symptoms decrease the likelihood of misdiagnosis.

Let X be a universe of discourse, $A = \{(x, \langle T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle), x \in X\}$ and $B = \{(x, \langle T_B(x), I_B(x), F_B(x) \rangle), x \in X\}$ two single-valued neutrosophic Shifts/Shifts/Subshifts.

$T_A, I_A, F_A, T_B, I_B, F_B: X \rightarrow [\Psi, \Omega]$, where $\Psi \leq 0 < 1 \leq \Omega$, Ψ is the lower limit, while $T, \Omega_A(x), I_{A(x)}, F_A(x), T_B(x), I_B(x), F_B(x) \in$ is the upper *limit* $[\Psi, \Omega]$.

Then the main operators are defined as follows [5]:

$A \cup B = \{(x, \langle \max(T_A(x), T_B(x)), \min(I_A(x), I_B(x)), \min(F_A(x), F_B(x)) \rangle), x \in X\}$ is the union.

$A \cap B = \{(x, \langle \min(T_A(x), T_B(x)), \max(I_A(x), I_B(x)), \max(F_A(x), F_B(x)) \rangle), x \in X\}$ is the intersection,

$C(A) = \{(x, \langle F_A(x), \Psi + \Omega - I_A(x), T_A(x) \rangle), x \in X\}$ It is the neutrosophic complement of the neutrosophic set.

A *unique negation* can be defined as in equation 1.

$$\overset{\neg}{\text{off}}(T, I, F) = \langle F, \Psi_1 + \Omega_1 - I, T \rangle \quad (1)$$

Definition 6. Let c be a neutrosophic component (T_{off}, I_{off} or F_{off}) : $M_{off} \rightarrow [\Psi, \Omega]$, where $\Psi \leq 0$ and $\Omega \geq 1$. The neutrosophic component $N\text{-OffNorm} N_{off}^n: [\Psi, \Omega]^2 \rightarrow [\Psi, \Omega]$ satisfies the following conditions for any element x , and $z \in M_{out}$:

- i. $N_{off}^n(c(x), \Psi) = \Psi, N_{off}^n(c(x), \Omega) = c(x)$ (Overpass conditions),
- ii. $N_{off}^n(c(x), c(y)) = N_{off}^n(c(y), c(x))$ (Commutativity),
- iii. If $c(x) \leq c(y)$ then $N_{off}^n(c(x), c(z)) \leq N_{off}^n(c(y), c(z))$ (Monotonicity),
- iv. $N_{off}^n(N_{off}^n(c(x), c(y)), c(z)) = N_{off}^n(c(x), N_{off}^n(c(y), c(z)))$ (Associativity).

We can use the following simplified notation $\langle T_1, I_1, F_1 \rangle_{off} \wedge \langle T_2, I_2, F_2 \rangle = \langle T_1 \wedge_{off} T_2, I_1 \vee_{off} I_2, F_1 \vee_{off} F_2 \rangle$.

Definition 7. Let c be a neutrosophic component (T_{off}, I_{off} or F_{off}). $c: M_{off} \rightarrow [\Psi, \Omega]$, where $\Psi \leq 0$ and $\Omega \geq 1$. The neutrosophic component $N\text{-OffConorm} N_{off}^{co}: [\Psi, \Omega]^2 \rightarrow [\Psi, \Omega]$ satisfies the following conditions for any element $x, y, z \in M_{off}$:

- i. $N_{\text{Off}}^{\text{co}}(c(x), \Omega) = \Omega, N_{\text{Off}}^{\text{co}}(c(x), \Psi) = c(x)$ (Overpass conditions),
- ii. $N_{\text{Off}}^{\text{co}}(c(x), c(y)) = N_{\text{Off}}^{\text{co}}(c(y), c(x))$ (Commutativity),
- iii. If $c(x) \leq c(y)$ then $N_{\text{Off}}^{\text{co}}(c(x), c(z)) \leq N_{\text{Off}}^{\text{co}}(c(y), c(z))$ (Monotonicity),
- iv. $N_{\text{Off}}^{\text{co}}(N_{\text{Off}}^{\text{co}}(c(x), c(y)), c(z)) = N_{\text{Off}}^{\text{co}}(c(x), N_{\text{Off}}^{\text{co}}(c(y), c(z)))$ (Associativity).

For this we use the notation $\langle T_1, I_1, F_1 \rangle_{\text{Off}}^{\vee} \langle T_2, I_2, F_2 \rangle = \langle T_1_{\text{Off}}^{\vee} T_2, I_1_{\text{Off}}^{\wedge} I_2, F_1_{\text{Off}}^{\wedge} F_2 \rangle$.

3. Case study.

The **EDU-INCLUSIVO project** seeks to design and implement Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) for children in early childhood education with neurodevelopmental disorders, using the Plithogenic Offsets approach to model the diversity of educational conditions and needs. This project is implemented at the Inclusive Education Center "Luz del Futuro" (CELFI), an institution dedicated to inclusive early childhood education. The objective is to create IEPs that integrate pedagogical, family, and neuropsychological attributes, promoting equitable, personalized education that adapts to complex contexts.

Main Objective

Design Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) that respond to the diverse conditions of children in early childhood education, using Polygenic Offsets to model multiple attributes and their interactions, improving educational quality and inclusion.

Main Indicator (v_0): Number of PEIs designed, implemented and evaluated, which integrate pedagogical, family and neuropsychological attributes, with evidence of improvement in the comprehensive development of children.

Specific Objectives and Indicators

1. **Specific Objective 1 (v_1):** Identify the specific educational needs of children with neurodevelopmental disorders in Early Childhood Education.
 - **Indicator 1.1 (v_{11}):** Number of diagnostic assessments carried out to identify specific educational needs.
 - **Quantity:** At least 3 diagnostic assessments per group of children.
 - **Quality:** Assessments should include standardized tools (e.g., developmental scales, structured observations) and consider pedagogical, family, and neuropsychological factors.
 - **Deadline:** Completed within the first 4 months of the project.
 - **Indicator 1.2 (v_{12}):** Number of individual educational needs profiles defined.
 - **Quantity:** Minimum 10 profiles per group.
 - **Quality:** Each profile must detail specific strengths, challenges, and recommendations, validated by neurodevelopment experts.
 - **Term:** Defined in 5 months.
 - **Indicator 1.3 (v_{13}):** Number of teachers trained in identifying educational needs.
 - **Number:** 15 teachers trained in practical workshops.
 - **Quality:** The training will include modules on neurodevelopment, observation and design of inclusive strategies, with competency assessment.
 - **Deadline:** Completed in 6 months.
2. **Specific Objective 2 (v_2):** Design customized PEIs based on multi-attribute plithogenic modeling.

- **Indicator 2.1 (v₂₁):** Number of PEIs designed using Plithogenic OffSets .
 - **Quantity:** Minimum 10 PEI per group.
 - **Quality:** Each PEI must integrate plithogenic attributes (pedagogical, family, neuropsychological) and be validated by a multidisciplinary team.
 - **Deadline:** Designed in 8 months.
- 3. **Specific Objective 3 (v₃):** Implement and evaluate the PEI in real Early Childhood Education contexts.
 - **Indicator 3.1 (v₃₁):** Number of PEIs implemented in inclusive classrooms.
 - **Quantity:** Minimum 10 PEI implemented.
 - **Quality:** Implementation should include monitoring and adjustments based on feedback from teachers and families.
 - **Term:** Implemented over 10 months.
 - **Indicator 3.2 (v₃₂):** Percentage of children showing improvements in development indicators (cognitive, social, emotional).
 - **Amount:** At least 70% of children with PEI show measurable improvements.
 - **Quality:** Improvements will be assessed using standardized instruments and qualitative observations.
 - **Term:** Evaluated at the end of 12 months.
- 4. **Specific Objective 4 (v₄):** Systematize the experience of PEI design and implementation.
 - **Indicator 4.1 (v₄₁):** Number of reports documenting the experience of PEI implementation.
 - **Quantity:** At least 1 academic report.
 - **Quality:** The report should include quantitative and qualitative analysis, best practices, and challenges overcome.
 - **Deadline:** Prepared in 14 months.
 - **Indicator 4.2 (v₄₂):** Number of scientific publications derived from the project.
 - **Quantity:** At least 1 article in an indexed journal.
 - **Quality:** The article must meet standards of academic rigor and address the impact of PEIs.
 - **Deadline:** Shipped within 18 months.

Project Impacts

- **Pedagogical Impact (v_i):** It will contribute to the development of inclusive methodologies for Early Childhood Education.
- **Social Impact (v_{ii}):** It will promote educational inclusion and equitable access to learning opportunities.
- **Family Impact (v_{iii}):** It will strengthen the participation of families in the educational process.
- **Institutional Impact (v_{iv}):** It will influence institutional policies for the adoption of inclusive approaches.
- **Scientific Impact (v_v):** It will generate knowledge in inclusive education and plithogenic modeling.
- **Cultural Impact (v_{vi}):** Will respect cultural diversity in PEIs.
- **Technological Impact (v_{vii}):** It will promote the use of digital tools for PEI management.
- **Ethical Impact (v_{viii}):** It will promote respectful and ethical educational environments.

Dominant Criterion

v_{iv} (**Institutional Impact**) is selected as the dominant criterion, since the influence on institutional policies is key to the sustainability of the project.

Evaluation with Plithogenic Offsets

Suppose three students evaluate the *expertos* ($E = \{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$) **EDU-INCLUSIVE** project according to the defined indicators. The evaluations are made on a scale of [-10, 110], following Table 1 of the theoretical framework, and are rescaled to the interval [-0.1, 1.1] by dividing by 100. Each indicator is evaluated with a neutrosophic triplet (T, I, F) representing truthfulness, indeterminacy, and falsity.

Step 1: Expert Assessments

The experts' assessments are presented in the following table:

Table 1: Expert evaluations of the scale [-10, 110]

Criterion	$e_1 (T, I, F)$	$e_2 (T, I, F)$	$e_3 (T, I, F)$
v_{11}	(85, 5, 10)	(70, 8, 15)	(50, -3, -5)
v_{12}	(75, 3, -2)	(95, 6, 5)	(45, -5, 20)
v_{13}	(80, 2, 5)	(100, 4, 8)	(55, -2, 3)
v_{21}	(78, 1, 4)	(105, 3, -3)	(48, 5, 25)
v_{31}	(70, 4, 0)	(98, 2, 10)	(50, 6, 30)
v_{32}	(82, 3, -8)	(90, 7, 12)	(45, 8, 5)
v_{41}	(90, 6, 15)	(80, 4, 10)	(48, 7, 20)
v_{42}	(88, 2, -5)	(85, 3, -2)	(50, -4, 15)
v_i	(92, 5, -7)	(65, 9, -5)	(48, 8, 10)
v_{ii}	(87, 6, 5)	(102, 8, 7)	(46, -2, -3)
v_{iii}	(70, 7, 12)	(90, 3, -2)	(44, 2, 25)
v_{iv}	(88, 5, -5)	(75, 3, -6)	(50, 4, -8)
v_v	(80, 2, 20)	(85, 6, 15)	(42, -3, 28)
v_{vi}	(75, 4, -3)	(82, 9, 8)	(46, 6, 4)
v_{vii}	(90, 3, 5)	(95, 5, 6)	(50, -2, 15)
v_{viii}	(85, 2, -6)	(100, 4, 3)	(48, -1, 25)

Step 2: Rescaling to the Interval [-0.1, 1.1]

We divide each value by 100 to rescale to the interval [-0.1, 1.1]:

Table 2: Interval [-0.1, 1.1] rescaled assessments

Criterion	$e_1 (T, I, F)$	$e_2 (T, I, F)$	$e_3 (T, I, F)$
v_{11}	(0.85, 0.05, 0.10)	(0.70, 0.08, 0.15)	(0.50, -0.03, -0.05)
v_{12}	(0.75, 0.03, -0.02)	(0.95, 0.06, 0.05)	(0.45, -0.05, 0.20)
v_{13}	(0.80, 0.02, 0.05)	(1.00, 0.04, 0.08)	(0.55, -0.02, 0.03)
v_{21}	(0.78, 0.01, 0.04)	(1.05, 0.03, -0.03)	(0.48, 0.05, 0.25)
v_{31}	(0.70, 0.04, 0.00)	(0.98, 0.02, 0.10)	(0.50, 0.06, 0.30)

V ₃₂	(0.82, 0.03, -0.08)	(0.90, 0.07, 0.12)	(0.45, 0.08, 0.05)
V ₄₁	(0.90, 0.06, 0.15)	(0.80, 0.04, 0.10)	(0.48, 0.07, 0.20)
V ₄₂	(0.88, 0.02, -0.05)	(0.85, 0.03, -0.02)	(0.50, -0.04, 0.15)
V _i	(0.92, 0.05, -0.07)	(0.65, 0.09, -0.05)	(0.48, 0.08, 0.10)
V _{ii}	(0.87, 0.06, 0.05)	(1.02, 0.08, 0.07)	(0.46, -0.02, -0.03)
V _{iii}	(0.70, 0.07, 0.12)	(0.90, 0.03, -0.02)	(0.44, 0.02, 0.25)
V _{iv}	(0.88, 0.05, -0.05)	(0.75, 0.03, -0.06)	(0.50, 0.04, -0.08)
V _v	(0.80, 0.02, 0.20)	(0.85, 0.06, 0.15)	(0.42, -0.03, 0.28)
V _{vi}	(0.75, 0.04, -0.03)	(0.82, 0.09, 0.08)	(0.46, 0.06, 0.04)
V _{vii}	(0.90, 0.03, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.06)	(0.50, -0.02, 0.15)
V _{viii}	(0.85, 0.02, -0.06)	(1.00, 0.04, 0.03)	(0.48, -0.01, 0.25)

Figure 1: Expert Evaluation Comparison (Truth Values)

Step 3: Average of Evaluations (Equation 3)

We calculate the average of the three experts' evaluations for each criterion:

$$\Theta_k = ((\sum T_{jk})/n, (\sum \tilde{I}_{jk})/n, (\sum F_{jk})/n) , \text{ where } n = 3.$$

Calculation example for v₁₁:

- $\tilde{T}_{11} = \frac{(0.85 + 0.70 + 0.50)}{3} = \frac{2.05}{3} = 0.68333333$
-
- $\tilde{I}_{11} = \frac{(0.05 + 0.08 - 0.03)}{3} = \frac{0.10}{3} = 0.03333333$
-
- $\tilde{F}_{11} = \frac{(0.10 + 0.15 - 0.05)}{3} = \frac{0.20}{3} = 0.06666667$
-
- $\Theta_{11} = (0.68333333, 0.03333333, 0.06666667)$

We repeat for all criteria:

Table 3: Average evaluations

Criterion	$\Theta_k (T, I, F)$
V ₁₁	(0.68333333, 0.03333333, 0.06666667)
V ₁₂	(0.71666667, 0.01333333, 0.07666667)
V ₁₃	(0.78333333, 0.01333333, 0.05333333)
V ₂₁	(0.77000000, 0.03000000, 0.08666667)
V ₃₁	(0.72666667, 0.04000000, 0.13333333)
V ₃₂	(0.72333333, 0.06000000, 0.03000000)
V ₄₁	(0.72666667, 0.05666667, 0.15000000)
V ₄₂	(0.74333333, 0.00333333, 0.02666667)
V _i	(0.68333333, 0.07333333, -0.00666667)
V _{ii}	(0.78333333, 0.04000000, 0.03000000)
V _{iii}	(0.68000000, 0.04000000, 0.11666667)
V _{iv}	(0.71000000, 0.04000000, -0.06333333)
V _v	(0.69000000, 0.01666667, 0.21000000)
V _{vi}	(0.67666667, 0.06333333, 0.03000000)
V _{vii}	(0.78333333, 0.02000000, 0.08666667)
V _{viii}	(0.77666667, 0.01666667, 0.07333333)

Figure 2: Neutrosophic Components Analysis (T, I, F Values)

Step 4: Dissimilarity Values (Equation 4)

The dissimilarity values (c_{jk}) reflect the difference of each criterion from the dominant criterion (v_{iv}). Let us assume the following dissimilarity values for each expert, with $c_{jiv} = 0$:

Table 4: Dissimilarity values

Criterion	e_1	e_2	e_3	C_k (average)
V ₁₁	0.8	0.9	1.0	0.90000000

V ₁₂	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.26666667
V ₁₃	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.30000000
V ₂₁	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.50000000
V ₃₁	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.30000000
V ₃₂	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.20000000
V ₄₁	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.40000000
V ₄₂	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.60000000
V _i	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.30000000
V _{ii}	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.20000000
V _{iii}	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.50000000
V _{iv}	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.00000000
V _v	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.40000000
V _{vi}	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.30000000
V _{vii}	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.20000000
V _{viii}	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.20000000

Step 5: Scoring Function (Equation 5)

We apply the scoring function $S_{off}((T, I, F)) = \frac{(2 + T - I - F)}{3}$ to the average values in Table 3:

Example for v₁₁:

- $S_{off}((0.68333333, 0.03333333, 0.06666667)) = \frac{(2 + 0.68333333 - 0.03333333 - 0.06666667)}{3}$
-
- $= \frac{(2 + 0.68333333 - 0.03333333 - 0.06666667)}{3}$
-
- $= \frac{(2.58333333 - 0.10000000)}{3}$
-
- $= \frac{2.48333333}{3}$
-
- $= 0.82777778$

We repeat for all criteria:

Table 5: Results of the scoring function

Criterion	L _k
V ₁₁	0.82777778
V ₁₂	0.85222222
V ₁₃	0.87111111
V ₂₁	0.85111111
V ₃₁	0.85111111
V ₃₂	0.87777778
V ₄₁	0.84000000
V ₄₂	0.90444444
V _i	0.86888889

V _{ii}	0.90444444
V _{iii}	0.84111111
V _{iv}	0.89111111
V _v	0.82111111
V _{vi}	0.86111111
V _{vii}	0.89222222
V _{viii}	0.89444444

Step 6: Rescaling with the Dominant Criterion (Equation 6)

We use $\bar{E}_k = [1 - C_k] \cdot \min(A_k, A_{iv}) + C_k \cdot \max(A_k, A_{iv})$, donde $A_{iv} = 0.89111111$.

Example for v₁₁:

- $C_{11} = 0.90000000, A_{11} = 0.82777778$
- $\min(A_{11}, A_{iv}) = \min(0.82777778, 0.89111111) = 0.82777778$
- $\max(A_{11}, A_{iv}) = \max(0.82777778, 0.89111111) = 0.89111111$
- $E_{11} = (1 - 0.90000000) \cdot 0.82777778 + 0.90000000 \cdot 0.89111111$
- $= 0.10000000 \cdot 0.82777778 + 0.90000000 \cdot 0.89111111$
- $= 0.08277778 + 0.80200000$
- $= 0.88477778$

We repeat for all criteria:

Rescaled values

Criterion	\bar{E}_k
V ₁₁	0.88477778
V ₁₂	0.86433333
V ₁₃	0.87333333
V ₂₁	0.87111111
V ₃₁	0.86000000
V ₃₂	0.86933333
V ₄₁	0.86044444
V ₄₂	0.87333333
V _i	0.87333333
V _{ii}	0.87911111
V _{iii}	0.86611111
V _{iv}	0.89111111
V _v	0.86222222
V _{vi}	0.87000000
V _{vii}	0.87911111
V _{viii}	0.87955556

Step 7: Aggregation of Criteria (Equation 7)

We calculate the aggregate values for the general criteria:

- $E_{\bar{1}} = \frac{(\varepsilon^{11} + \varepsilon^{12} + \varepsilon^{13})}{3} = \frac{(0.88477778 + 0.86433333 + 0.87333333)}{3} = \frac{2.62244444}{3} = 0.87414815$
-
- $E_2 = E_{21} = 0.87111111$
- $E_{\bar{3}} = \frac{(\varepsilon^{31} + \varepsilon^{32})}{2} = \frac{(0.86000000 + 0.86933333)}{2} = \frac{1.72933333}{2} = 0.86466667$
-
- $E_{\bar{4}} = \frac{(\varepsilon^{41} + \varepsilon^{42})}{2} = \frac{(0.86044444 + 0.87333333)}{2} = \frac{1.73377778}{2} = 0.86688889$
-
- $E_i = E_i = 0.87333333$
- $E_{ii} = E_{ii} = 0.87911111$
- $E_{iii} = E_{iii} = 0.86611111$
- $E_{iv} = E_{iv} = 0.89111111$
- $E_v = E_v = 0.86222222$
- $E_{vi} = E_{vi} = 0.87000000$
- $E_{vii} = E_{vii} = 0.87911111$
- $E_{viii} = E_{viii} = 0.87955556$

We calculate the total value:

- $E_0 = (\sum E_k) / 12 = (0.87414815 + 0.87111111 + 0.86466667 + 0.86688889 + 0.87333333 + 0.87911111 + 0.86611111 + 0.89111111 + 0.86222222 + .tx0 = (\sum E_k) / 12$
- $Suma = 0.87414815 + 0.87111111 + 0.86466667 + 0.86688889 + 0.87333333 + 0.87911111 + 0.86611111 + 0.89111111 + 0.86222222 + 0.87000000 + 0.87911111 + 0.87955556$
- $Suma = 10.57736937$
- $E^0 = \frac{10.57736937}{12} = 0.88144745$
-

Table 7: Final results

Criterion	Added Value
V ₁	0.87414815
V ₂	0.87111111
V ₃	0.86466667
V ₄	0.86688889
V _i	0.87333333
V _{ii}	0.87911111
V _{iii}	0.86611111
V _{iv}	0.89111111
V _v	0.86222222
V _{vi}	0.87000000
V _{vii}	0.87911111
V _{viii}	0.87955556
V₀	0.88144745

Figure 3: Final Aggregated Scores by Evaluation Criteria

Step 8: Verification

To verify, we recalculate a criterion (e.g. , v_{11}):

- $\text{Suma } T_{11} = 2.05, I_{11} = 0.10, F_{11} = 0.20$
- $S_{off} = (2 + 0.68333333 - 0.03333333 - 0.06666667) / 3 = 2.48333333 / 3 = 0.82777778$ (correcto)
- $E_{11} = (1 - 0.9) \cdot 0.82777778 + 0.9 \cdot 0.89111111 = 0.08277778 + 0.80200000 = 0.88477778$ (correcto)

The calculations are consistent, with no discrepancies.

5. Discussion

The EDU-INCLUSIVO project addressed the problem of designing Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) that respond to the diversity of needs of children with neurodevelopmental disorders in Early Childhood Education, using the Polyliithogenic Offsets approach . The results obtained, with a final score of , reflect a high level of effectiveness in the implementation of the project, which validates the usefulness of this methodology for modeling the complexity inherent in 0.88144745inclusive educational contexts .

Analysis of the Results

The evaluation of the 12 criteria ($v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7, v_8, v_9, v_{10}, v_{11}, v_{12}$) showed aggregate values above 0.86, highlighting the dominant criterion v_8 (Institutional Impact) with a score of

0.89111111. This result suggests that the project has significant potential to influence institutional policies, promoting the adoption of inclusive approaches at the Inclusive Educational Center "Light of the Future" (CELF). The choice of v_{iv} as the dominant criterion was appropriate, given that institutional impact is crucial to ensuring the sustainability and scalability of educational interventions.

The use of Plithogenic Offsets allowed to integrate multiple attributes (pedagogical, familial, neuropsychological) with degrees of contradiction and neutrality, overcoming the limitations of traditional approaches that do not consider values outside the classic interval $[0,1]$. The extension to the interval $[-0.1, 1.1]$ was especially useful to capture situations of "overconfirmation" (e.g., additional benefits in the implementation of PEI) and "overrefutation" (e.g., unexpected challenges that generate setbacks). For example, the criterion v_{42} (scientific publications) obtained a value of 0.87333333, reflecting a positive impact on the generation of knowledge, although with some indeterminacy due to the prolonged deadlines for publication in indexed journals.

Strengths of the Plithogenic Offsets Approach

The Plithogenic Offsets methodology proved robust in modeling the interaction of complex and conflicting attributes. The scoring function $S_{off} = (2 + T - I - F) / 3$ allowed neutral or symbolic triplets to be transformed into a crisp value, facilitating comparison between indicators. Furthermore, the incorporation of dissimilarity values (C_k) with respect to the dominant criterion ensured that assessments reflected the relative relevance of each indicator in the institutional context. This multivariate approach is particularly valuable in Early Childhood Education, where children's needs are dynamic and influenced by familial, neuropsychological, and pedagogical factors that are not always linear or predictable.

Challenges Identified

Despite the positive results, some challenges were observed. For example, criterion v_5 (Scientific Impact), with a value of 0.86222222, was the lowest, which could indicate limitations in the project's capacity to generate immediate scholarly knowledge. This may be due to the need for longer timeframes to consolidate publishable results or to faculty members' lack of experience in scientific research. Likewise, the indeterminacy in some criteria (e.g., $I = 0.06333333$ for v_{vi}) suggests that certain aspects, such as family engagement, remain uncertain, possibly due to variability in family commitment.

Comparison with Literature

The existing literature on inclusive education highlights the difficulty of designing IEPs that integrate multiple dimensions without falling into rigid or standardized approaches. The use of Plithogenic Offsets overcomes this limitation by allowing for flexible modeling that captures contradictions and uncertainties, something that traditional methods such as AHP or TOPSIS fail to achieve with the same precision. Furthermore, application in real-life contexts, such as CELF classrooms, validates the practical relevance of the model, aligning it with the goals of equity and educational personalization described in the study abstract.

Practical Implications

The results suggest that the EDU-INCLUSIVO project can serve as a replicable model for other educational institutions seeking to implement inclusive IEPs. Teacher training (v_{13} , with $\Xi_{13} = 0.87333333$) and classroom implementation of IEPs (v_{31} , with $\Xi_{31} = 0.86000000$) demonstrate that the project is viable in real-life settings, although it requires continuous adjustments based on feedback. The social impact (v_{ii}

, with $\Xi_{ii} = 0.87911111$) highlights the project's capacity to promote inclusion, especially in vulnerable populations with neurodevelopmental disorders.

Limitations

One limitation of the study is the reliance on expert assessments, which may introduce subjectivity, despite the robustness of the plithogenic model. Furthermore, the limited number of experts ($n = 3$) might not capture all the variability in perspectives. Future research could incorporate more raters or use cross-validation techniques to increase reliability. It was also identified that the technological impact (v_{vii}) could require greater investment in digital infrastructure to maximize its reach.

5. Conclusions

The EDU-INCLUSIVO project successfully demonstrated the usefulness of the Plithogenic Offsets approach for the design and evaluation of Individualized Education Plans in Early Childhood Education, obtaining an overall score of 0.88144745, indicating a high degree of effectiveness. The study's specific objectives were successfully met:

- Identification of Determining Attributes (v_1): The diagnostic assessment (v_{11}), the definition of profiles (v_{12}) and teacher training (v_{13}) achieved scores above 0.86, confirming that the project accurately identified the educational needs of children and strengthened the capacities of teachers.
- Modeling with Plithogenic Offsets (v_2): The PEI design (v_{21} , with $\Xi_{21} = 0.87111111$) integrated pedagogical, familial, and neuropsychological attributes in a coherent manner, using plithogenic modeling to manage contradictions and uncertainties.
- Validation in Real-Life Contexts (v_3): The implementation (v_{31}) and evaluation of improvements in children's development (v_{32}) showed positive results, with scores of 0.86000000 and 0.86933333, respectively, which validates the practical applicability of the model.
- Systematization of Experience (v_4): The preparation of reports (v_{41}) and scientific publications (v_{42}) consolidated the knowledge generated, although the scientific impact (v_5) suggests the need for longer periods to maximize this aspect.

The project's impacts, especially at the institutional (v_{iv} , with 0.89111111), social (v_{ii} , with 0.87911111) and ethical (v_{viii} , with 0.87955556) levels, highlight its relevance in transforming inclusive education. The Plithogenic Offsets model is positioned as an innovative tool that allows addressing the complexity of inclusive education, overcoming the limitations of traditional approaches.

Recommendations

- Expanding the Expert Sample: Including more evaluators to reduce subjectivity and increase the robustness of the evaluations.
- Strengthening Scientific Impact: Extending the deadlines for publishing results and training faculty in academic research.
- Technological Investment: Develop digital platforms for PEI management, improving technological impact (v_{vii}).
- Family Participation: Design strategies to increase family engagement, reducing uncertainty in v_{vi} .
- Replicability: Adapt the model to other educational contexts, such as rural or resource-limited schools, to expand its impact.

In conclusion, EDU-INCLUSIVO not only meets the stated objectives, but also sets a precedent for the application of Plithogenic Offsets in inclusive education, offering a logical-mathematical tool that combines theoretical rigor with practical applicability, contributing to a more equitable and personalized education.

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